

Mutual Exclusivity in Classical Probability and Related Information in Entangled States

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Classical probability is often introduced as a set of positive numbers (≥ 0 , ≤ 1) such that their sum is 1. We suggest that an extra key idea is the mutual exclusivity of the probabilities. In particular, if a coin is heads-up, it cannot be tails. This seems obvious, but in physical situations one may be able to identify clear mutually exclusive states/situations in terms of one process/event which are no longer mutually exclusive in terms of a second process. The two different processes, however, occur together. Thus, these two processes are related, and the non-mutually exclusive situation should contain information about the mutually exclusive one. As an example, we consider 2-slit interference. The mutually exclusive scenario is the motion of a particle/photon through one slit or the other. The non-mutually exclusive scenario is the interaction of the particle/photon with both slits if slit widths/separations are on the order of \hbar/p , where p is the magnitude of momentum. Thus, our argument is that the non-mutually exclusive scenario should contain information about the probabilities of the mutually exclusive one. This suggests that there should exist a general mathematical framework for this and we seek this framework in this note.

Mutually Exclusive Classical Probability

Classical probability involves positive numbers (≥ 0 , ≤ 1) which add to 1. We suggest that another key feature is the mutual exclusivity of the labels (states) associated with the probability. For example, if a coin is heads, it cannot be tails etc. This appears obvious, but there are physical situations in which there may be clear mutually exclusive events while at the same time different events do not distinguish between the mutually exclusive ones. We discuss the 2-slit experiment in the next section as one such example.

Two-Slit Experiment

We argue that the two slit experiment involves a mutually exclusive probability scheme regarding the event of a particle/photon passing through one slit or the other. Thus:

$$P(\text{slit 1}) + P(\text{slit 2}) = 1 \text{ and in fact } P(\text{slit 1}) = .5 \quad ((1))$$

This holds for any wavelength. The issue is that the distinguishability (or mutual exclusivity) does not hold for interactions for all wavelengths. If $\hbar/p \ll$ slit width/separation, then not only does the photon/particle pass through one slit or the other, but it only interacts with that slit. If \hbar/p is of the order of the slit width/separation, then the photon/particle can interact with both even though it passes through one or the other. In such a case, one obtains an entangled state which should contain information about interactions with both slits. This information should ultimately let one know the probability to pass through one slit or the other, we argue. Unlike classical probability, the entangled state is a physical one and not a mathematical OR situation of two mutually exclusive states, like a tossed coin being either heads up or tails, but represents

by a sum which does not represent a physical state. The question then becomes: Given a physical entangled state, how does one mathematically extract the classical probability associated with one slit and the other?

Mathematical Framework for Linking an Entangled State to a Classical Mutually Exclusive Probability

A two-slit interference pattern is based on an entangled state which is created when a photon/particle interacts with both slits. This probability pattern is displayed on a screen far away from the two-slits and is not related to whether the photon/particle passed through one slit or the other. One observes a distribution of photon/particle number versus x on the screen if the photon/particle initially moves along the y -axis and the 2-slit apparatus is aligned along the x .

As a result, one may consider the entangled state to have probability type values (related to intensity and not the probability of passing through one slit or the other at each x,y). Given that the photon/particle interacts with each slit, and the two are identical, one would guess that each contributes the same kind of effects. In fact, one would also guess that the probability to pass through slit 1 is .5 and through slit 2, .5. These values should, however, be obtainable from the entangled probability, we argue.

First one may suggest writing the following:

Entangled intensity function related to probability $(x,y) = F1(x,y)+F2(x,y)$ where 1 represent slit 1 and 2, slit 2 ((2))

$F1$ and $F2$, however, cannot be positive numbers because otherwise ((2)) is simply the recipe for classical OR states (heads or tails) and not a physical, entangled state. Thus, at the very least, $F1$ and $F2$ must take on both positive and negative values we argue. This makes them unusual as classical probability is not negative. An approach is ultimately needed to make $F1+F2$ positive for all x,y .

{ If one is uncomfortable with a negative $F1$ or $F2$ at certain x,y points, one may consider a free particle. The fact that the free particle interacts with both slits if widths/separations are of the order of \hbar/p means that there is something probabilistic in space about the interaction process of the photon/particle itself. In other words, there should be a $G(x,y)$ which could be positive or negative associated with the free particle. The free particle, however, moves through space at a constant speed treating each dx point in the same manner and so one cannot have different probability values at different x points. This suggests that one use:

$\exp(ipx)$ ((3))

to describe its probability. This has a modulus of 1 and contains two functions, $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ which are both positive and negative.}

Thus, one does not need to be concerned about $F1(x,y)$ (or $F2(x,y)$) being negative at different x,y points. The positive/negative feature creates the entangled state. The question then becomes: How can one extract information about each slit, namely the probability to pass through one or the other? A first step seems to be to integrate out x,y . Now, if $F1(x,y)$ and

$F_2(x,y)$ can be positive or negative at different x,y points, then the sum may be also. The probability for slit 1 must be positive and somehow associated with F_1 and for slit 2, with F_2 . In order to obtain a positive result for both it seems that one might suggest squaring F_1+F_2 and then integrating i.e.:

$$(F_1(x,y)+F_2(x,y))^2 = F_1^2 + F_2^2 + 2F_1F_2 \quad ((4))$$

To obtain mutual exclusivity, one then requires that: $\int dx dy F_1(x,y)F_2(x,y) = 0 \quad ((5))$

Simply taking the modulus does not allow one to isolate F_1, F_2 .

In other words, one has orthogonal functions associated with the mutually exclusive events when used in an entangled state. These orthogonal functions, being both positive and negative at different x,y values create an entangled state, but one may mathematically disentangle it by squaring and integrating. As a result, the classical probability emerges as a square of the entangled type of probability.

The integration over x,y is key as without integration ((4)) yields values at all $x-y$ points and is guaranteed to be an overall positive number. Thus, it may serve to describe an intensity distribution along a screen while an integration yields the contribution of each slit and no longer contains x,y . The squared function ((4)) serves to demonstrate two probabilities which coexist: the intensity probability on a screen and the probability to pass through one slit or the other. The two probabilities are positive, but the sense of entanglement as a physical state requires an intertwining which cannot be achieved by simply adding two positive numbers. This would yield a classical OR (heads or tails) scenario, not an entangled state. Thus, positive-negative functions are needed for entanglement, but they must be orthogonal so that mutual exclusivity appears when $F_1 + F_2$ is squared to obtain a classical probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics may involve situations which involve a classical mutually exclusive probability associated with one kind of event (probability to pass through one slit or the other in a 2-slit experiment) and an entangled state (photon-particle interacting with both slits if \hbar/p is of the order of the slit widths/spacing. The entangled state is a physical state (unlike the mathematical one of .5 heads + .5 tails in a coin toss), yet it should still be able to reveal the classical probability associated with passing through one slit or the other.

An entangled state involves interactions with both slits, we argue, and so one might suggest writing a sum: $F_1(x,y)+F_2(x,y)$. These cannot, however, be positive at all x,y otherwise one has a classical probabilistic OR situation and not physical entanglement. This suggests F_1 and F_2 being positive and negative at different x . This may give rise to F_1+F_2 also being positive and negative suggesting an intensity distribution. The only problem is that F_1+F_2 may be negative and a probability must be positive. This suggests at the simplest: $(F_1+F_2)^2$ which yields a cross-term $2F_1F_2$. If one wishes to find the probabilities of passing through slit 1 or 2, then this involves integration over $dx dy$ and so F_1 and F_2 should be orthogonal functions. (Note: One

cannot simply take the modulus of F_1+F_2 because it does not separate out probabilities for passing through slit or the other.) This then leads to an entangled state being represented by orthogonal functions (taking both positive and negative values) and being associated with an classical probability scenario (slit 1 or slit 2), but entangling because of the positive and negative values. A squaring process is necessary to obtain a positive probability and orthogonal functions F_1, F_2 in order to obtain mutual exclusivity of classical probability upon integration.